

Kinetics of ω -Chlorination of 1-Acetonaphthone by *N*-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one with and without Chloride Ions

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The kinetics of chlorination of 1-acetonaphthone with *N*-chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (NCP) in the absence of chloride ions and also in the presence of a sufficient excess of chloride ions have been studied. In the former case, the order with respect to [NCP] is one and those with respect to [substrate] and $[H^+]$ are fractional. In the latter case, the order with respect to [NCP] and $[Cl^-]$ each is zero and that with respect to [substrate] and $[H^+]$ each is unity. The kinetic data have been rationalised, suitable mechanisms proposed and thermodynamic parameters E_a , $\Delta S^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ have been reported for both the cases.

THOUGH many papers have been published on the oxidation of ketones, only a limited number of papers¹⁻³ are there on the halogenation of aryl alkyl ketones using *N*-halo compounds. Recently, the use of NCP as oxidising agent⁴⁻⁶ has been reported. In the present study, we report the kinetics of chlorination of acetonaphthone with NCP.

Experimental

The NCP was prepared and purified as described earlier⁴. 1-Acetonaphthone was prepared⁷ and purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. 134–35°/2.5 mm. Ethanol was freed from carbonyl compounds by distilling over silver oxide. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

The kinetic measurements were made by estimating aliquot portions of the reaction mixture for the NCP iodometrically using starch as indicator. The pH measurements were made using the ITL DPH-14 digital pH meter.

The stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 1 in NCP and acetonaphthone. The product ω -chloroacetonaphthone was identified by tlc by comparison with an authentic sample.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic aspects in the absence of chloride ions :

Effect of change in [NCP] : The chlorination of acetonaphthone with NCP in EtOH–H₂O (3 : 1, v/v) in presence of 0.6 M perchloric acid was studied. The order with respect to [NCP] was found to be one as evidenced by a linear plot of log ($a-x$) versus time. The pseudo-first order rate constants decreased with the increase in the initial

concentration of NCP (Table 1). This may be due to the decrease in the effective concentration of the reactive species^{8,9}.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF NCP CONCENTRATION

[Substrate]=0.0281 M, $[HClO_4]=0.610$ M, Temp.=40±1°, EtOH–H₂O=3 : 1 (v/v)

[NCP] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.05	5.19
1.58	4.65
2.10	3.95
2.68	3.55
3.16	3.02

Effect of change in [substrate] : Increase in [substrate] was found to increase the rate of the reaction. The plot of log k_{obs} versus log [substrate] was a straight line with a slope 0.84 ($r=0.99$) showing a fractional order with respect to [substrate] (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION

[NCP]=0.002 M, $[HClO_4]=0.592$ M, Temp.=40±1°, EtOH–H₂O=3 : 1 (v/v)

[Acetonaphthone] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ / [sub] ^{0.84}
1.15	2.40	1.02
1.73	3.84	1.01
2.30	4.09	0.98
2.88	5.24	1.03
3.46	6.00	1.01

Effect of change in $[H^+]$: Increase in $[H^+]$ keeping the ionic strength, [substrate] and [oxidant] constant, increased the rate of the reaction linearly with a slope 0.95 ($r=0.99$) showing a fractional order with respect to $[H^+]$ (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION

[NCP]=0.002 M, [Substrate]=0.024 M, Temp.=40±1°, EtOH-H₂O=3:1 (v/v)

[HClO ₄] ^a × 10 dis.	[NaClO ₄] ^b × 10 dis.	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k × 10 ⁴ [H ⁺] ^{0.99}
0.90	4.20	0.74	7.29
1.90	8.80	1.50	7.27
8.95	1.15	8.02	7.80
5.10	0.00	8.85	7.80

^a Concentration of HClO₄ dissociated was obtained from the measured pH value ^b Dissociation of NaClO₄ was taken same as that of HClO₄.

Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant :

The rate of the reaction was found to increase linearly with increase in ionic strength (Table 4). Decreasing the dielectric constant by increasing the percentage of EtOH showed a small decrease in the rate (Table 5).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH

[Substrate]=0.0286 M, [NCP]=0.004 M, [HClO₄]=0.98 M, Temp.=40±1°, EtOH-H₂O=3:1 (v/v)

[NaClO ₄] × 10	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
2.17	1.24
3.86	1.73
4.49	1.84
5.51	2.16

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

[Substrate]=0.0216 M, [NCP]=0.002 M, [HClO₄]=0.45 M, Temp.=40±1°

EtOH %	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
60	2.91
65	2.78
70	2.51
80	2.05

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction was studied at five different temperatures (30, 35, 40, 45 and 50°). The values of E_a, ΔS^* , ΔH^* and ΔG^* were determined and found to be 74.086 kJ mol⁻¹, -0.0237 kJ K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, 71.483 kJ mol⁻¹ and 78.902 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Effect of [Chloride ion] : Addition of a little amount (0.005 M) of chloride ion increased the rate four-fold and the rate constant attained a limiting value on further addition of chloride ions.

Kinetic aspects in the presence of excess chloride ions :

Effect of [NCP] and [substrate] : The reaction was studied at varying [NCP] keeping [substrate], [H⁺] and [Cl⁻] constant. The pseudo-zero order rate constants obtained from the linear plots of [NCP] against time were constant indicating zero order with respect to NCP (Table 6). The pseudo-zero order rate constants were calculated at

different initial concentrations of the substrate. The rate constant divided by [substrate] gave a constant value showing the order with respect to [substrate] to be one.

TABLE 6—EFFECT ON NCP AND SUBSTRATE IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION

[HCl]=0.1247 M, EtOH-H₂O=3:2 (v/v), Temp.=40±1°

[NCP] × 10 ⁴ M	[Substrate] × 10 ³ M	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	k ₀ × 10 ⁶ [Substrate]
0.56	2.86	2.189	—
1.12	2.86	2.031	—
1.69	2.86	2.189	—
1.12	1.18	1.104	9.857
1.12	1.77	1.524	8.609
1.12	2.86	2.031	8.604
1.12	2.94	2.584	8.620

Effect of [H⁺] : The kinetics of the reaction was studied with different concentration of hydrogen ion keeping [NCP], [substrate] and [Cl⁻] constant. The rate increased linearly with the increase in [H⁺]. The order with respect to [H⁺] was one (Table 7).

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF [H⁺] IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION[Substrate]=0.0166 M, [NCP]=0.001 M, [HCl]=0.09521 M, Temp.=40±1°, EtOH-H₂O=3:2 (v/v)

[H ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ³ M	pH	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	k ₀ × 10 ⁶ [H ⁺]
4.18	1.14	7.24	1.799	2.484
8.25	1.05	8.91	2.198	2.461
12.53	0.89	13.90	3.104	2.407
16.70	0.80	15.80	3.745	2.370

Effect of [Cl⁻], ionic strength and dielectric constant : Changes in [Cl⁻], ionic strength and dielectric constant showed negligible effect on the rate.

Effect of temperature : The reaction was carried out at five different temperatures (35, 38, 40, 43 and 45°). The thermodynamic parameters E_a, ΔS^* , ΔH^* and ΔG^* were found to be 97.168 kJ mol⁻¹, -0.048 kJ K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, 94.564 kJ mol⁻¹ and 109.686 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Mechanism :

By rationalising the above results two mechanisms have been proposed for the chlorination of acetonephthone.

In absence of chloride ions : It is assumed that the direct attack of NCP on the enolic form of the ketone gives an intermediate ion-pair, which is then decomposed to products in a slow step (Scheme 1). Since the rate of the reaction decreases with the increase in initial concentration of NCP, the possibility of NCPH⁺ as the reactive species^{4,5} is ruled out and hence NCP itself is considered as the reactive species. This is obvious from equation (2)¹⁰.

Scheme 1

The rate law as per Scheme 1 is derived by assuming a pre-equilibrium complex (equation 3) between the enolic form and NCP. It can be shown that

$$\text{rate} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_2 [\phi-C(=O)-CH_3][H^+][NCP]}{1 + K_2 [\phi-C(=O)-CH_3][H^+]}$$

$$\frac{1}{\text{rate}} = \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_2 [\phi-C(=O)-CH_3][H^+][NCP]} + \frac{1}{K_1 k_2 [NCP]}$$

To test the validity of this rate law, 1/rate was plotted against 1/[substrate] keeping $[H^+]$ and $[NCP]$ constant, and against $1/[H^+]$ keeping [substrate] and $[NCP]$ constant. Both these Michaelis-Menton plots gave straight lines ($r=0.99$) supporting the formation of the Arrhenius intermediate (ion-pair) complex (equation 3) and the fractional orders with respect to [substrate] and $[H^+]$. The high negative entropy of activation is an additional

support for the polar intermediate complex formation.

In the presence of chloride ions: Enolisation is considered as the rate determining step. The formation of Cl_2 from protonated $NCP^{4,5}$ and the attack of the former on the enolic form of the ketone are fast steps (Scheme 2). The rate law is

Scheme 2

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